

AN INEQUALITY CONCERNING THE SMARANDACHE FUNCTION

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Abstract. For any positive integer n , let $S(n)$ denote the Smarandache function of n . In this paper we prove that $S(mn) \leq S(m) + S(n)$.

Let N be the set of all positive integers. For any positive integer n , let $S(n)$ denote the Smarandache function of n . By [2], we have

$$(1) \quad S(n) = \min\{k \mid k \in N, n \mid k!\}.$$

Recently, Jozsef[1] proved that

$$(2) \quad S(mn) \leq mS(n), \quad m, n \in N.$$

In this paper we give a considerable improvement for the upper bound (2). We prove the following result.

Theorem. For any positive integers m, n , we have $S(mn) \leq S(m) + S(n)$.

Proof. Let $a = S(m)$ and $b = S(n)$. Then we have

$$(3) \quad n \mid b!,$$

by (1). Let x be a positive integer with $x \geq a$, and let

$$(4) \quad \binom{x}{a} = \frac{x(x-1)\dots(x-a+1)}{a!}$$

be a binomial coefficient. It is a well known fact that $\binom{x}{a}$ is a positive integer. So we have

$$(5) \quad a! \mid x(x-1)\dots(x-a+1),$$

by (4). Further, since $m \mid a!$, we get from (5) that

$$(6) \quad m \mid x(x-1)\dots(x-a+1),$$

for any positive integer x with $x \geq a$. Put $x = a + b$. We see from (3) and (6) that

$$(7) \quad mn \mid b!(b+1)\dots(b+a) = (a+b)!.$$

Thus we get from (7) that $S(mn) \leq a+b=S(m)+S(n)$. The theorem is proved.

References

1. S.Jozsef, On certain inequalities involving the Smarandache function, Smarandache Notce J. 7(1996), No.1-3, 3-6.
2. F.Smarandache "A function in the number theory", "Smarandache Function J". 1(1990), No.1, 3-17.